

Promoting Socio-emotional Skills in Initial Teacher Training: An Emotional Educational Programme

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Developing socio-emotional skills is essential for improving university students' quality of life and subjective well-being. These skills also play a crucial role in initial teacher education, as they are responsible for their students' cognitive, emotional and social development. The objective of the present study is to analyse the perceived impact of an emotional education programme for teachers in training. A total of 56 student teachers, from seven different master's degree programmes, completed a six-session programme. The evaluation was conducted through an experiential portfolio, which included the challenges and dynamics experienced in terms of emotional experience, the meaning of these experiences, and the difficulties and gains. The results revealed that, despite some difficulties, participation in the programme was considered by the participants as contributing to their emotional literacy, such as the ability to express and understand their own emotions and those of others, and to a growing sense of empathy and connectedness. This study highlights the importance of continuously investing in teachers' socio-emotional growth and competence during their training and teaching careers.

Keywords: social and emotional learning, socio-emotional skills, emotional education programme, initial teacher training, sense of belonging

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Introduction

Socio-emotional skills are essential for academic success and, later, for economic success (Korbel & Paulus, 2017). Consequently, efforts to promote social and emotional learning (SEL) have increased significantly in recent years (Shriver & Weissberg, 2020). These efforts identified five interrelated domains that comprise the SEL framework: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision-making (CASEL, 2015). Self-awareness refers to our ability to accurately recognise our own emotions, thoughts and impulses, as well as determine how these influence our behaviours. Self-management is about being able to effectively regulate our emotions, manage our thoughts and take responsibility for our behaviour in a variety of situations. Social awareness refers to the ability to empathise with others, to put ourselves in their shoes and to understand different backgrounds and cultures. Relationship skills correspond to establishing and maintaining healthy and rewarding relationships with different people and communities. Finally, responsible decision-making relates to the ability to make thoughtful, constructive and socially acceptable choices about our behaviour and interactions with others (CASEL, 2015). Therefore, implementing SEL requires a systemic approach, integrating social and emotional development into every part of student learning (CASEL, 2019).

Teaching is demanding, and recognising the difficulties teachers experience in their profession is particularly important to promote interventions that can maintain, or restore, teachers' emotional well-being (Savina et al., 2021). The constant emotional demands teachers face from students, parents, colleagues, and school administrators are well known (Cross & Hong, 2012). In Portugal, the most recent study on the psychological health and well-being of primary and secondary school students and teachers revealed several difficulties experienced by teachers. These included significant signs of restlessness, irritability, feelings of sadness or depression, and difficulty taking initiative or relaxing (Direção Geral da Educação, 2022). Given the centrality of emotions to learning and classroom management, and as teaching is an intrinsically emotional experience, teachers need to be socioemotionally competent (Valente, 2022). Several studies have shown that fostering in teachers not only substantially impacts their teaching performance and capacity to build positive pedagogical relationships with their students, but also improves their psychological well-being and mental health (Antão & Veiga Branco, 2012; Li et al., 2021). As various authors advocate, this training should occur as early as possible, preferably during teachers' initial training (Castillo-Gualda et al., 2017; Pérez-Escoda et al., 2013; Valente & Almeida, 2020).

Additionally, the quality of social relationships and the need to belong reflect both the individual's well-being and the quality of the school's social ethos (Kachchhap & Horo, 2021). An individual defines himself or herself according to his or her social environment and that their interactions with the environment determines their respective future (Dearing et al., 2006). For teachers, getting the attention of other teachers (and administrators), being accepted and included in the teaching team, and feeling supported by them, are fundamental to feeling a sense of belonging (Kachchhap & Horo, 2021). When teachers experience this social environment, they feel more satisfied and committed to their work, are more successful in achieving their

goals, and perform better (Rezaee et al., 2018). Furthermore, interpersonal relationships can positively or negatively affect teachers' experiences of social connectedness (Bower et al., 2015). Consequently, negative feelings about the organisation in which one works can be reduced through social connectedness (Alanoglu & Karabatak, 2021). In addition, training in the elements that help develop social connectedness can facilitate the emergence of positive feelings in teachers in training.

In summary, teachers encounter high levels of stress in the school context (Rey et al., 2016) and face constant emotional demands in their professional activities (Cross & Hong, 2012). Given the central role of emotions in teacher efficacy, well-being, and psychological health (Savina et al., 2021; Valente, 2022; Vesely et al., 2013) and how these are impacted by a social environment fostering a sense of community, the school environment can possibly lead to higher levels of teacher satisfaction, engagement, and efficacy (Kachchhap & Horo, 2021).

Objectives of the study

Emotional competence and social connectedness are seen as a critical element in the training of initial teachers (Kachchap & Horo, 2021; Valente & Almeida, 2020). Given the absence of both dimensions in the formal curriculum of teacher training in the context of the present study, the authors developed an emotional education programme (EEP). They implemented its pilot version in the Developmental Psychology course unit taught in the first semester of each master's programme course in initial teacher education at the University of Minho (Portugal). The main objective was to promote the emotional skills of prospective teachers and their social connectedness within the group. The EEP was also designed to encourage students to reflect on some of the most important and impactful aspects of their training for their professional and personal development.

The present paper presents the qualitative evaluation of the programme, namely which activities in the programme did students found most significant impactful for them, the reason(s) why, and the words that better describe their overall experience.

Method

Participants

A total of 87 students from seven different teaching courses participated in the EEP. They were all attending the curricular unit of Developmental Psychology, taught in the first semester of the teacher training master's degree at the University of Minho (Portugal). However, as not every student participated in the entire programme, only the portfolios of the 56 students who attended at least four sessions were considered.

Intervention

The EEP consisted of six 90 minutes sessions, held one week apart and they were all facilitated by the teacher trainer of the course unit. The first three sessions were focused mainly on the Self, exploring the students' personal trajectories and academic courses. In the "Approach the line" session, students were invited to take a step further if the content of each statement pronounced by the facilitator represented their own experiences or

feelings (e.g., “Take a step further if you ever felt humiliated by a teacher”; “Take a step further if you feel that you owe someone an apology”). During the “Life Line” session, students were asked to draw their personal and academic trajectories and identify the most significant episodes and people (e.g. affectionate, protective, mind opening versus hurtful, overwhelming, traumatic) at different stages of their school and personal life. In the "Lego" session, students were encouraged to build a representation of the main character (the "hero" or "villain") of one of the positive and negative episodes they had identified in their "Life Line". As they built their characters, students were asked to think about why these people (and episodes) were so meaningful to them and what they would want to say to each of them if they had the chance to meet them face to face. In addition, students were asked to pay attention to their emotions (bodily reactions: internal subjective experiences, facial expressions, physiological reactions), feelings (conscious experiences) and behaviours during the activity. Afterwards, each student was instructed to write them down in their portfolio and to reflect on their reactions and the main lessons they learned from them.

The second part of the programme was designed to encourage the students to "open up" to the Other. Thus, in the fourth session - "The Human Library" - the group was invited to actively listen to two or three "books" (guests) who shared a meaningful chapter of their lives. Afterwards, they had the opportunity to ask questions that could elicit the emotional, cognitive and behavioural responses of the book protagonists, as well as the impact of these "chapters" on their lives. The main objective was to practice attending skills, namely passive and active listening, exploration skills, empathy and compassion (and eventually self-disclosure) were the main goals of this session.

The fifth session - "Look at what I am not saying" - explored non-verbal behaviour and its power and relevance in human communication. Through a series of mimic exercises, the students were challenged to convey and decode the messages of their peers based only on their body language. The goals of the fifth session were to facilitate participants' skills in non-verbal communication. The sixth and final session - "Wrap up" - integrated the experiences and insights (individual and group) gained in the previous sessions and tried to transfer them to their personal and future professional life as teachers. In this final session, a game was played where students were tasked with answering questions such as, the way they react emotionally to certain situations, the way they communicate and express themselves, the relationship with their future students and colleagues, identifying and responding to students' emotional needs, our conflict management. In a group of colleagues, each student had to take a card and face a specific challenge, e.g. to solve a hypothetical problem concerning their interactions with a pupil, class or other teachers; to identify emotions, feelings and/or behaviours in certain situations; to think about strategies to deal with their or others' emotional The aim was to integrate, apply and reflect on the five domains suggested by the CASEL framework, namely self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision-making.

Procedures and Data Analysis

Participants were invited to keep an experiential portfolio. Following each session, they were asked to respond to a set of open-ended questions about some of the most important aspects of the previous session (e.g.,

feelings, insights about themselves and others). The portfolios were delivered one month after the intervention and the end of the semester. The portfolios were analysed using content analysis method (Bardin, 2016) with a phenomenological approach of data analysis. First, two members of the research team read the portfolio separately, identified units of meaning to operationalise the search for relevant data, and classified them into emerging categories. When discrepancies arose, a third researcher helped reach a consensus. Once this phase was completed, each researcher separately labelled the text's main ideas as codes and counted the number of references in each emerging category. After extracting the initial codes, the data were reduced and meaningfully organized as presented in the next section.

Results

Table I presents the frequency of the sessions students found most impactful. The first and fourth sessions were the most impactful for the overall group, as confirmed by 12 and 10 students respectively.

Table I. Most impactful session/activity of the EEP

Session	Frequency
Approach the Line (Session 1)	12
Human Library (Session 4)	10
Look at what I am not saying (Session 5)	8
The Life Line (Session 2)	7
Lego (Session 3)	7
Wrap up (Session 6)	2
All equally important	4
None specifically impactful	2
No answer/Does not identify any specific session/episode	2
Other (mainly “disconnected” answers, no clear meaning)	4
Total	58

In the first session, students were asked to approach the line if the situation described by the facilitator (e.g., likes and dislikes, personal characteristics, life experiences) matched their own experiences (e.g., having other siblings, having been a victim of bullying, having lost a loved one during the pandemic). In this activity, the group was lined up next to each other on both sides of the line and paired with a classmate standing directly in front of them. This way, while positioning themselves according to the situation elicited by the facilitator (and taking a step forward if it described their own experience), they could immediately see – and be seen – by their partners. Furthermore, if they looked to the side, they could see the rest of the group’s and their peers’ reactions to each situation. Thus, they had to engage with their own and each other’s experiences, learn more

about their partners, and consider, among other things, the similarities and differences in their repertoire. The following testimonies illustrate some of the students' most significant experiences during this activity.

This first activity was very impactful. I think I will always remember it. It was a beautiful moment of sharing, full of emotions and connection amongst people that hardly knew each other (s23).

I felt that I got to know my classmates better since we've had almost all our classes online in the first year. I even had the chance to talk to a classmate who was by my side and never had the chance to talk to (s27).

I'm not sure if it was because it was the first session or because it forced me to revisit so many moments that I thought were resolved but weren't... It was like opening a 'small box' [the loss of her grandfather when she was a child] that was a little bit painful. But sincerely, I think it was good for me; I think it was a chance to reorganise my ideas and put things together inside my 'little box' (s30).

I have seen my classmates' vulnerabilities and have realised that 'I am not alone'. ...This activity impacted me because it made me think about episodes of my life that I thought were 'forgotten' or 'closed' (...) To remember these striking episodes of my life made me realise that I don't feel any resentment anymore regarding the people involved. ...So, this experience exponentially contributed to my realizing the evolution that happened more recently in terms of my emotional development. I also was moved to see the emotions of other classmates. ...Although I didn't know them, I felt like hugging them, and, no doubt, that contributed to an understanding of the group. And, of course, it made me relativise my own problems, which felt futile and tiny [compared to the others] (s32).

It was beautiful to...observe the connection that immediately emerged in the first session, something that, definitely, I was not expecting to see. Despite knowing superficially the colleague that was in front of me [during the activity]...It was the perfect impetus to start developing a friendship between the two of us that, nowadays, represents one of my strongest relationships at the university (...). None of us judged, criticised, or asked any intrusive questions about the activity; on the contrary, each of us respected the other's space but demonstrated that we were there to listen whenever we needed to talk about some of the themes that were brought up [during the activity] (s44).

In the second-most cited session – “The Human Library” – students pointed to several aspects that particularly impacted them during the presentation of some of the books that they have had the chance to “read”. The following excerpts show the most impactful aspect of the activity and what the participants learned from it:

The most impactful was the book that made me cry. The book told us about an episode where he suffered continuously from bullying during adolescence because of his looks...and that could well be my chapter. I could only relive the moments I'd suffered inside and outside of school while listening to the story, and think about all the people who had hurt me... During this activity, I've realised that I still haven't gotten over this trauma because I still have difficulties accepting my body and I wonder a lot about what the others will think about my looks (s36).

I've felt involved with that story, as if it were mine. It was an inexplicable and unique sensation. It was outstanding in the sense that it made me relive certain memories and helped me get to know myself better, to realise that it is a fragility that I have and that there is nothing wrong with showing it; on the contrary, it's even good to let our emotions out. It was a story that also helped me better understand the people around us, because there is a story that can explain why this person behaves or

acts in a certain way, and that sometimes we think they are a little inappropriate." Based on this, I have realised that we should not judge a book by its cover; we have to give of ourselves for others to know us and to get to know the others, because each one of us is as we are, and that makes us incredible and unique human beings (s55).

It was, no doubt, when, in the Human Library, the members of my group opened up and exposed some of their own experiences. This was the moment that most impacted me positively because it made us feel more united as a group, as colleagues, and as friends. To get to know others and have the trust to share aspects of our lives with them, we must share parts of ourselves that will also become a part of theirs. In this case, it compelled us to cultivate greater intimacy and connection between us. ...I am grateful to them for having trusted me with such important and delicate information about their lives, just as I am grateful for having had the opportunity to share mine (s13).

The participants were also asked to identify at least three representative words that best described their experience in participating in the EEP. The results are summarised in Table II and consider the intrapersonal and interpersonal processes that emerged from the analysis of their descriptors. The participants used words to describe their participation in the EEP that referred to both internal (intra) and relational (inter) aspects of the experience, and, in both cases, emotional and cognitive processes and outputs emerged as the main descriptors. If we look more closely at the intrapersonal processes, we can see that different emotions (many of them generally referred to as “emotions”; $n = 14$) were present when they faced the challenges posed by the programme’s activities. Some of these emotions were intense, surprising, painful, or stressful. However, despite these activities’ disturbing or disarming effects, many students made emotional gains and achieved success due to these confrontational moments and the emotional processes they evoked. Some students mentioned the feelings of resilience, happiness, joy, and a sense of overcoming. Others even felt relief when, for example, they had the opportunity to revisit their stories and deal with their fears, share their feelings with others, put them on paper, or get them “off their chests”.

In cognitive terms, the words chosen by the students to describe the programme referred to an opportunity for self-examination ($n = 8$). The programme was also seen as a chance for students to reflect on their thoughts, behaviours, and feelings or to gain some insights and get to know themselves and each other better ($n = 3$). Many of the students identified greater self-awareness ($n = 18$) resulting from their participation in the programme. This self-knowledge emerged through the memories evoked when revisiting some episodes (good or bad) in their lives, actively listening to others’ stories ($n = 7$), or the empathic exercise of “walking in each other’s shoes” ($n = 17$). Furthermore, they became aware of the need to learn more about feelings, their role in each individual’s psychological health and well-being, as well as on their relationships with others ($n = 9$).

Table II. Words that better represent the students' participation in the EEP

Category	f	Category	f
Intrapersonal		Interpersonal	
Processes	56	Processes	35
<i>Cognitive</i>	29	Sharing	11
Memories	4	Active listening	7
Introspection	8	Empathy	17
Consciousness	3		
Reflection	11		
Integration	3		
<i>Emotional</i>	27		
Emotions	14		
Intense	2		
Challenging	2		
Anxiety	6		
Pain	3		
Outputs/Gains	73	Outputs/Gains	14
<i>Cognitive</i>	29	Humanization	2
Knowledge (about the self and the others)	19	Union/Belongingness	11
Learning (about self, emotional development, the role of emotions and feelings)	9		
Focus (on priorities)	1		
<i>Emotional</i>	22		
Resilience/Overcoming	12		
Release	2		
Nostalgia	3		
Happiness, joy, well-being	5		
Self-regulation (of emotions and feelings)	1		
Motivation	1		
Additional tools	3		
<i>Self-perception</i>	22		
Self confidence	3		
Self-respect	1		
Self-knowledge	18		
Other/Non Classified	7		

The interpersonal aspects of the experience was expressed by “sharing”, the second most frequently mentioned word (n = 11), along with “empathy” and “active listening”. These terms were used to characterise the relational processes that emerged during the programme, which led to many of the resulting interpersonal

benefits, particularly the connectedness, mutual understanding, sense of unity, and sense of belonging described by 11 participants.

Discussion

The students' perceptions of the most meaningful activities, processes and gains activated by or resulting from their participation in the EEP, show how relevant and beneficial an SEL programme can be for their social and emotional development as prospective teachers. Their reflections on their experiences indicate that the programme impacted four of the five domains encompassed by the SEL framework (CASEL, 2015), namely self-awareness ("I realised that I still have not got over this trauma..."; "...this experience contributed exponentially to realising the evolution that has happened more recently in terms of my emotional development"); social awareness ("It was a story that also helped me better understand the people around us..."; "Although I did not know them, I felt like hugging them..."); relationship skills (e.g., "None of us judged, criticised or asked intrusive questions about the activity..."); and responsible decision-making (e.g. "...each of us respected the other's space but showed that we were there to listen if we needed to talk about some of the issues that were raised"; "[it made me] realise that it's a fragility that I have and that there is nothing wrong with showing it; on the contrary, it is even good to let our emotions out").

The participating students reported that the EEP provided them with the opportunity to reflect on their own stories, to recognise and express their emotions and feelings (whether in the group or more individual exercises), and to become aware of their own resources, limitations, strengths, and vulnerabilities (and their commonalities with the others). According to their descriptions of the cognitive, emotional, and social processes that took place during the EEP, the different activities offered during the six sessions allowed them to engage in a significant process of introspection, reflection, and integration of past experiences that led them to a higher level of awareness, self-knowledge, and, in some cases, confidence to overcome their future (personal, relational, and professional) challenges.

These processes and gains were facilitated by the group, whether in situations where they had the opportunity to listen to each other's stories, to share their own, or by observing their verbal or non-verbal, conscious or unconscious attempts to communicate their thoughts and feelings. The knowledge that they were not alone, that their most significant experiences were shared by their peers, as well as the opportunity to hear the inspiring stories of others, not only gave them hope and strength to face their own challenges but also helped them revisit these challenges and move forward. The influence of the Other seems to extend to situations where students realised that their peers could also be a resource if they have been through similar situations and had developed coping skills that they could learn or benefit from.

During some of the activities, students had the opportunity to intensely experience their common humanity in the form of joys, fears, vulnerabilities, and conquests (e.g. "It was beautiful to observe (...) the connection that immediately emerged in the first session"; "I am grateful to them for trusting me with such important and sensitive information about their lives, as I am grateful for the opportunity to share mine"). These episodes seem to have contributed to the emergence of a sense of (comm)union, empathy, and mutual

understanding that many of these students described (e. g. "...greater intimacy and connection between us"; "I felt involved in this story as if it were my own. It was an inexplicable and unique feeling"). Their accounts lead us to the concept of sense of belonging described by Kachchhap and Horo (2021), a factor that, along with the quality of social relationships, is of paramount importance to the individual and the environmental well-being and strength.

The EEP seems to have also contributed to the emergence of a sense of 'social connection' (Lee & Robbins, 1998) or 'social connectedness' (Bower et al., 2015) among the participants: "... it made us feel more united as a group, as colleagues and as friends. Getting to know others and having the confidence to share aspects of our lives with them (...) that will also become part of theirs". Alanoglu and Karabatak's (2021) claim that the development of social connectedness during initial teacher training can promote the development of positive feelings in prospective teachers. The integration of EEP into the formal curriculum of initial teacher training can thus make an important contribution for the next generation of teachers in developing more positive feelings about oneself and others, their profession, and the educational community they be part of.

Despite the promising potential of the programme, it is also important to pinpoint its limitations. First, it should be noted that all students participated voluntarily. Therefore, it is not known whether these participants differed in their motivation or other characteristics from those who chose not to participate. In addition, as a pilot study, it involved a relatively small sample of students and was conducted at only one university. Therefore, these results should be interpreted with caution, as they have limited generalisability and seriously limit our ability to draw firm conclusions about the programme's effectiveness. Furthermore this study only explored the participants' experiences and views of the programme and a more rigorous, experimental study making of randomized control trial, will be necessary to examine the impact of programme on students' outcomes. However, as indicated earlier, the present study was designed as a pilot to explore the relevance and contribution of EEP in initial teacher training on the basis of students' experiences.

The length of the programme could also be a limitation, as six sessions may be insufficient to work on deeply all the emotional skills included in CASEL's framework. Therefore, future implementations could try to add supplementary sessions and work more intensively on the more complex emotional skills. Studies on the design and implementation of SEL programmes emphasise the importance of the "taught dose". If the dose is insufficient, the desired effects will not be achieved (Wisconsin Center for Education Research, 2006). In this sense, the duration of participation in the programme was about two months, so the sustainability of its results is unknown.

Conclusion

The results of this pilot study highlight the importance of fostering student-teachers' emotional skills and social connectedness at early stages of their training, and supporting them to build their professional identities and develop a sense of belonging to their new professional communities. The participants' perceptions of the quality of the relationships built within the group during the intervention, characterised by mutual understanding, humanity, empathy, and solidarity between members, suggest that self-awareness served as a

catalyst for the changes that occurred throughout all the session. The EEP has in its genesis an evolutionary process based on moments of reflection and sharing, and this can be a good starting point to build social connection and a sense of belonging. This helps to reduce potential negative feelings and leads to higher levels of professional satisfaction, commitment, and success among teachers (Alanoglu & Karabatak, 2021; Bower et al., 2015; Rezaee et al., 2018). Higher levels of emotional competence are strongly associated with the quality of teachers' relationships with their students and the whole school community, and therefore the efficacy of their pedagogical practices, the ability to prevent and manage conflicts in the classroom, and a lower prevalence of burnout, clearly support the need to invest in teachers' emotional education and to integrate it as a core component in teacher training programmes. In the short term the programme also supports prospective teachers at the start of their training to deal with the multiple demands, new roles and tasks that the pre-service teacher has to deal with in this critical stage. The development of socio-emotional skills helps them to cope with the frustrations, setbacks and uncertainties of their first attempts at teaching and to accept more readily the certainties and uncertainties that underpin their professional development and the teaching profession.

Disclosure

The authors confirm that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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